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Artist Videos

2022-2023

Deliverable 4.5.1

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A-Place

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Artist Videos (2022-2023)

Version 1.0

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Executive Summary

This is a report on the video art productions created during the fourth year of the project which have been commissioned by the LOOP Barcelona festival and screened in its 2023 edition.

Two video works were commissioned:

- by Pau Faus, as artist-in-residence, to carry out a research work focused on dialogue between nature and technology. The video work [“The machine and the flower”](#) was filmed at two locations: the interior and exterior of the ALBA Synchrotron, an impressive structure located on the outskirts of Barcelona, considered the most complex research machine in the southwest of Europe.

- by Camila Flores-Fernández, winner of the 2023 open call on video art. The video [“We are here”](#) is a documentary film that delves into the life stories of twelve young refugees currently seeking international protection due to their sexual orientation or gender identity in the city of Brussels. The film is the result of an active collaboration between the Brussels-based youth work organization Queers on the Move (QOM), the young refugees, and the filmmaker.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and target group

Over the last twenty-one years, Screen Projects has organized LOOP Barcelona, an international meeting point to showcase the latest artistic productions related to video art, the moving image and the ever-expanding field of audiovisual artworks. From its very start, one of its foremost concerns has been how to offer artists the opportunity to reflect and enrol in practices that strengthen their social implication. Therefore, most of the artistic practices that LOOP supports tend to capture the complex layers that animate public space and the various constructs that define people's sense of belonging, as well as intimating the ways in which they relate to the world. In short, we assume that artists are always eager to uncover the symbolic construction of place, a hidden layer that seldom manifests itself in material terms, and this is precisely what LOOP intends to help bring out in a bid to widen the reach of creative placemaking.

This report contains a description of the process leading to the commission of the two video art productions presented in the A-Place section of the 2023 edition of the LOOP festival: ["The machine and the flower"](#) by Pau Faus and ["We are here"](#) by Camila Flores-Fernández.

1.2. Contribution of partners

Screen Projects, the organization that manages the LOOP Barcelona festival, has been the partner in charge of organizing the open call and selecting the artists-in-residence. Representatives from La Salle and Screen Projects were part of the jury of the open call. Other A-Place partners have contributed to the dissemination of the call and of the awarded work.

1.3. Relations to other activities in the project

As part of the communication work of the project A-Place, both videos were presented at the LOOP Festival press conference held at Casa Elizalde in Barcelona on November 13, 2023, and were subsequently exhibited at the same venue throughout the following month.

2. Artist-in-residence production

2.1. Intent and goals

The artists-in-residence grant aims to produce a video artwork that explores the notion of place.

Pau Faus, a filmmaker, visual artist, and architect, served as the appointed artist-in-residence for the year 2023. During his tenure as an architect, his fascination with contemporary art movements, including situationism, land art, and relational aesthetics, led him to rediscover architecture and urbanism beyond the confines of academia. In 2009, he started the exhibition of his works, and to carry out projects and workshops at various local and international art venues.

In 2013, responding to the social and political climate in Spain, he transitioned from contemporary art for activism, joining the prominent nationwide movement against evictions, the PAH (Plataforma de Afectados por la Hipoteca [Mortgage Victims Platform]). Within this movement, he co-founded Comando Vídeo, a collective dedicated to video communication in social movements. Together, they directed the featurette “¡Sí se puede! Siete días en PAH Barcelona” (“Yes, we can! Seven days with PAH Barcelona”), in 2014. Later, in 2016, he gained acclaim for his first feature film “Alcaldesa” (“Mayoress”), which depicts the journey of an activist running for the position of mayor in Barcelona. His second feature film, “Fauna” (2023), is a science fiction fable exploring the relationships between humans, animals, and science in post-pandemic times.

2.2. Commissioned project

Pau Faus

The machine and the flower (2023, 35 min)

<https://www.a-place.eu/en/media-production/55>

Pau Faus's work during his LOOP residency encapsulates a dialogue between nature and technology. Filmed at two distinct locations—the interior and exterior of the [ALBA Synchrotron](#), an impressive structure situated on the outskirts of Barcelona and recognized as the most intricate research facility in the southwest of Europe—the video unfolds a compelling conversation with Juan Arnau, an astrophysicist, philosopher, and specialist in Eastern cultures, who staunchly defends humanism in the face of contemporary technological distractions.

Figure 1. "The machine and the flower" by Pau Faus. View of the exhibition at Casa Elizalde Barcelona. Source: LOOP Festival

The video was [exhibited](#) at Casa Elizalde from November 16 to December 23 (Figure 1). On November 27, there will be a [dialogue](#) of Pau Faus with Victoria Sacco, curator, and project coordinator at LOOP Barcelona, and Pau Subirós, screenwriter, director, and producer, on the theme "Science, technology and documentary perspective".

3. Open call production

3.1. Intent and goals

In order to support the creative endeavours of artists, LOOP Barcelona launched for the fourth and last time during the A-Place project, a call for proposals to attract and engage a wide range of participants to generate ideas about the concept of place in all its possible expressions and dimensions. The call aimed to support projects that critically examine established ideas and traditional approaches to the symbolic creation of space and sense of belonging. These types of artworks are intended to promote public discussion and shape social constructions. The ultimate goal is to promote the idea of active citizenship and shared public spaces, which are central to the A-Place project.

3.2. Open call process

The call was announced on December 2022 and it was advertised in the [A-Place website](#) (Figure 2) and in the [LOOP website](#) (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Announcement of the call on A-Place website

Figure 3. Announcement of the call on LOOP website

The documentation of the call (Figure 4) included:

- a) A short description of the project A-Place
- b) A presentation of LOOP Barcelona, the issuer of the call
- c) The object and purpose of the call
- d) The terms and conditions - Participants Eligibility
 - Project Characteristics
 - Awarded Grant
 - Selection Criteria
 - How to Submit
 - Application Deadline and Calendar
 - Acceptance of Terms

Figure 4. Documentation of the open call

3.3. The jury

To select a winner for the A-Place Open Call 2023 (Figure 5), we formed an international jury comprised of:

- **Leandro Madrazo.** Project Coordinator of A-Place, full professor and head of the research group ARC Engineering and Architecture at La Salle. His teaching interests focus on the integration of architecture theory and representation, art and media, as well as on housing studies and design methodology. He has been the coordinator of various research projects, such as HOUSING@21.EU (2003-06), OIKODOMOS (2007-09, 2010-11), and OIKONET (2013-16), all funded by EACEA. He has been co-coordinator of Prohabit (2015-18) and has led the UMVA (Unidad Móvil de Vídeo Arquitectura) programme, carried out in collaboration with LOOP Festival, from 2012 to 2017.
- **Ramón Parramón.** Artist, researcher and professor. Director and founder of IDENSITAT @idensitat a collective project, through which he develops his research practice as an artist and cultural manager. He is the deputy director of EINA Centre Universitari de Disseny i Art de Barcelona, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona. Previously, he has been director of the ACVIC. Centre d'Arts Contemporànies (2010-2018) and has been part of the curatorial team of Co-habitar at Fabra i Coats Centre d'Art Contemporani de Barcelona (2016-2017). He specializes in the intersection of artistic practices and social spaces and has extensively published on the topic, including articles in various books and magazines.
- **pli-è collective.** A research and curatorial group formed by Eva Paià, Marina Ribot Pallicer and Angelica Tognetti. Since February 2021 they managed the Sala d'Art Jove, a space promoted by the Catalan Youth Agency of the Catalan Government.
- **Victoria Sacco.** LOOP A-Place Coordinator and LOOP City Screen Coordinator, curator and professor. She is the editor of *Muntadas. Con/Textos III: An Anthology of Critical Texts*, published by La Virreina Centre de la Imatge (2020), and writes for the journal *La Maleta de Portbou*. Since 2010, she has been teaching at the ESDi School of Design in Barcelona and has been collaborating in LOOP Barcelona festival since 2014. Previously, she worked as project

coordinator and later as co-director of the arts and science foundation Quo Artis. She is currently collaborating with Pedro G. Romero and Antoni Muntadas.

The criteria to select the works were the following:

- The artistic merit of the proposal.
- The consolidated professional career of the artist/s.
- The innovative way of exploring the concept of creative placemaking.
- The implication of local social agents, associations or collectives.
- The understanding of all the aspects and viability implicit in a video production of this kind.

To streamline the jury's task, LOOP conducted a pre-selection of projects, with Victoria Sacco, artistic director of the festival, and Mila Pesce, the A-Place coordinator at LOOP, taking charge of short-listing the projects. However, the jury was provided with the entire list of submitted productions, in case they wanted to review any of them. The final selection meeting took place in person on March 7, 2023, at the LOOP headquarters.

3.4. Awarded production

We received 103 project proposals (33 in the 2020 call, 63 in 2021, 73 in 2022), 15 of them from European countries. The diverse range of projects showcased various approaches to constructing and involving communities in art-based placemaking processes. The sheer quantity and quality of the proposals have made the jury's deliberation process both exciting and complex. We extend our gratitude to all who submitted proposals for their interest and efforts.

The jury decided to award the project entitled "We are here", by Camila Flores-Fernández. The [announcement](#) was done on March 7, 2023. (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Announcement of the winner in LOOP and A-Place Website

Camila Flores-Fernández (Lima, 1996) is a Peruvian researcher, multimodal anthropologist and visual artist based in Belgium. Her practice comprises writing, video and mixed media to explore intersectionality and identity.

Camila Flores-Fernández

We Are Here (2023, 23 min)

<https://www.a-place.eu/en/media-production/54>

Figure 6. "We are here" by Camila Flores-Fernández. View of the exhibition at Casa Elizalde Barcelona. Source: LOOP Festival

["We are here"](#) provides insight into the experience of immigrating through the lens of two queer refugees, who are each in different stages of this process in Brussels. Through a collective creation method, the immigrants get to choose how to tell their story. This documentary delves into each step of the immigration process, as well as how the queer immigrants carve out their space in the urban landscape they find themselves in. By narrating, sharing, and shedding light on their origins, they can make themselves, their identities, and their stories visible, allowing them to establish their own sense of belonging derived from a unique set of experiences.

The video was [exhibited](#) at La Casa Elizalde, Barcelona, from 16 November to 23 December, 2023.

On December 13, a conversation between the artist and Victoria Sacco took place at Casa Elizalde under the title ["Documentary Film, Migration and Queer Subjectivity"](#).